

Annex IV

Scope

Annex to *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars*

CONTENTS:

The scope of a given decision is the maximal set of things possibly impacted by it. In *Annex IV Scope*, numerical estimations are proposed for the elements potentially impacted by the decision humans may or may not take regarding the extrasolar advent of life, as defended in *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars*.

Methodology is detailed for each point in the evaluation. Causation is differentiated between what may happen via the media of massive transmitters, and what may happen through the exchange of signals. Direct impacts are separated from indirect ones, requiring the existence of extraterrestrial life (ET) or intelligence (ETI). Evaluations are categorised as straight, strong or weak, depending on their reliability. All ET and ETI dependent evaluations are categorised as weak. Synthetical tables and figures are proposed.

A synthesis on the work provided in this annex is performed in *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars, IV) EVALUATION*.

Table of contents

Introduction	2
1-Definition	3
2-Position regarding Ethics	4
3-Robustness of the evaluation.	4
4-Transmission Type	5
a) Impact via massive transmitters	5
b) Impact via non-massive transmitters	8
5-The hypothesis of extraterrestrial life	9
a) Stars hosting planets in their habitable zone	9
b) Specific caution regarding the distribution of life and intelligent life	10
c) Decision regarding the evaluation of ET related parameters	13
ETI, as a class of ET, adds the bellow sensibility:	14
6-Points of evaluation	15
7-Evaluation of scope	16
A) Massive transmitter	19
A.a) Intentional	19
A.b) Incidental	20
A.c) Synthesis on massive transmission	21
B) Non-massive transmitters	22
B.a) Evaluation of the potential for non-massive transmissions	22
B.b) Figures for detectability estimations	24
B.c) Synthesis on non-massive transmission	25
C) Impacted Elements	26
C.a) incertitudes are growing	26
C.b) Accessible mass and amount of stars within reach	27
C.c) Potentially impacted elements, via massive transmitters:	27
C.d) Potentially impacted elements, via non-massive transmitters:	29
Bibliography	33

List of Figures

<i>Fig 1. Drawing: Estimations of frequency from search space are dubious when distribution are not continuous</i>	11
<i>Fig 2. Equivalent photometric magnitude as a function of distance and transmitting civilisation class: detectability range of a class 1.5 civilisation</i>	24
<i>Fig 3. Equivalent photometric magnitude as a function of distance and transmitting civilisation class: detectability range of a class 3.5 civilisation</i>	24
<i>Fig 4. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via massive transmitters, by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.</i>	28
<i>Fig 5. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via non-massive transmitters, by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.</i>	31

List of Tables

<i>Table 1. Estimated escape velocities, from the gravitational wells Earth is bound to, with reference to Earth position.</i>	7
<i>Table 2. Synthesis on maximal total, frequency and range of transmissions via physical, massive elements such as rocks, spaceships and probes</i>	20
<i>Table 3. Synthesis of maximal range for extrasolar transmissions via electromagnetic waves of all kinds(Laser, radio...).</i>	24
<i>Table 4. Evaluation of incertitudes</i>	25
<i>Table 5. Potentially impacted elements, via massive transmitters.</i>	27
<i>Table 6. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via non-massive transmitters by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.</i>	30

Introduction

The potential impact of the expansion of life as we know it on Earth, in the accessible universe, is important. Beyond this statement, delopped in *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars*, we propose that our minds require numbers, and representations to identify with, so as to conceptualise what is at stake.

The annex *Scope* is addressing this question and proposes to evaluate the scope embodied by the decision humans may make from the kingmaker position detailed in *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars*.

To evaluate the potential impacts, we categorise causation by relying on two approaches: transmission type, and dependence upon the hypothesis of extraterrestrial life. These approaches help as they segregate properties useful to the evaluation of potential impacts, while also informing on the robustness of the evaluation itself.

After clarifying in 1-Definition, the definition of scope in our context, we will, in 2-Position regarding ethics, adopt a neutral moral position. In 3-Robustness of the evaluation, a choice is made regarding the characterisation of the uncertainties in this work, allowing for the estimation of an upper bound to uncertainties, while saving detailed uncertainty calculations. The scope will then be addressed through transmission type, and dependency to the hypothesis of extraterrestrial life.

4-Transmissions type will distinguish in (4.a), causation happening via massive elements such as probes, spaceships or rocks, travelling at lower speeds, and in (4.b), non-massive signals, travelling at the speed of light. In 5-The hypothesis of extraterrestrial life, the separation will be made between direct impacts and impacts dependent on the hypothesis of extraterrestrial life (ET) or intelligence (ETI). In (5.a) an estimation of the amount of stars hosting planets in their habitable zone is selected, and after emphasizing in (5.b) that any evaluation related to the latter is weak by nature, a decision is taken regarding the evaluation of potential impacts dependent on ET. The typical ET and ET used for evolution are parameterised in (5.c).

In 6- Points of evaluation, five points of evaluation are chosen, for which the potentially impacted elements, constitutive of the scope of the possible decision regarding life advent out there, will be evaluated.

In 7- Evaluation of scope, the evaluation itself will take place, determining at each point of evaluation, the potential range accessible via massive (7.A), then non massive transmitters (7.B), before investigating a selected array of noticeable potentially impacted elements (7.C).

No synthesis nor conclusion are proposed to this annex as a section synthesizing the work proposed here, is available in *Kingmakers, life's gateway to the stars, IV, B) An existential choice*, along with a figure¹ presenting the results of this study.

¹ *Kingmakers, life's gateway to the stars* Fig 11, p67

1-Definition

The scope of something is according to *Oxford Languages*, “the extent of the area or subject matter that something deals with or to which it is relevant.”²

In order to evaluate the potential impact of the decision to accelerate, forbid, delay, let happen, or take no decision regarding the access of life as we know it to the extrasolar space, I propose an attempt to evaluate the scope of this decision. We are trying to answer the question: “What difference does it make, that we care, or not, of releasing life out?”. In this context, we retain the below working definition:

Scope: *the scope of a given decision is the maximal set of things possibly impacted by the decision*

The scope of the decision to cook a cake twenty minute more, does not tell us if it is a good idea or not, but provides information. People, tastebuds, kitchen elements, cleaning products may be impacted. Then the quantity of impacted people, may be very dependant to important hypotheses such as whether the cake is likely to take fire or not, the presence of fire detectors or not, the presence of a tank of propane nearby, the likeness of the kitchen to be located in the warehouse of an ammonium nitrate depot. More, the typology of the involved causation is important in this evaluation. The consequences of the overcooking are probably negligible when considering the gustative quality as a media for causation, and critical when considering the possible ignition.

2-Position regarding Ethics

In the below discussion, we are investigating the maximal set of things possibly impacted. We will not consider whether the impacts are good ones, that we should be thriving to realise, or bad ones, we should avoid at any cost, should such a distinction exist. The scope, as defined, is non determinant regarding the moral status of the decision itself. It does not inform regarding the goodness or badness of it, but on the typology of the impacted elements, and their quantity. As such, it carries valuable information regarding the importance of the decision: for what type

² Definition by Oxford Language

of things ? Is this decision important for a lot of things ? depending on what hypotheses ? by which means ?

We will take no side in the ethical debate and leave it to moral philosophers, ethicists, and politicians to consider the possible goodness or badness of influencing the spread of life. Our only purpose will be to envision the typology and the size of the potential impacts, of releasing life, extrasolar.

3-Robustness of the evaluation.

In this work we differentiate straight, strong and weak evaluations. These notions are associated with an upper bound estimation for associated uncertainties, leading to an estimation of upper bound for the uncertainty of the presented results.

Straight

Straight evaluation relates to parameters exclusively dependent on a retained model, and are considered as reliable as the model itself. Examples: the evaluation of the volume within the event horizon with the selected de Sitter model, is a direct evaluation. The amount of stars within a 1000 ly radius as calculated from GAIA Archive, is a direct evaluation.

Strong

Strong evaluation relates to parameters derived from the retained model, through an external estimation considered as reliable. Examples: the evaluation of the total mass or energy within the calculated event horizon is considered strong. The evaluation of the quantity of planets orbiting the stars within a 1000 ly radius as calculated from GAIA Archive is considered strong.

Weak

Weak evaluations refers to evaluation proposed for their interest, and the identification that these allow, while bearing little to very little reliability. Examples: the quantity of potentially existing civilisations within the event horizon, or the quantity of biospheres orbiting the stars within the 1000 ly radius.

For various reasons, detailed in 4-C all estimations related to the distribution of extraterrestrial life are considered to be weak.

Associated uncertainties

While a complete calculus of uncertainties would be valuable, using referenced uncertainties for each of the parameters at each of the points of evaluation, it has been considered given the

limited manpower and the allowance for errors before the validity of the discussion is lost³, that a high bound evaluation would be sufficient. As such, while often way better than this, the estimated parameters classified as straight or strong, are considered to have incertitudes on one order of magnitude. Reality is considered less than ten times bigger, or ten times smaller, than those estimations from the literature.

As will be detailed in [7.C.a incertitudes are growing](#), those overestimated incertitudes pile up to large uncertainties in the ultimate results, ranging up to 4 orders of magnitude regarding volumes, for evaluations considered as strong.

4-Transmission Type

By dividing simply the possible processes by the nature of the involved transmitter, a segregation by transmission type allows to distinguish two classes of speeds of processes, and of size of accessible universe, as limited by different horizons⁴. We will distinguish:

- Causation via **non-massive transmitters** (lasers, radio waves, visible light, changes in reflectivity..) which is happening at the speed of light, and is limited in range, to the event horizon
- Causation via **massive transmitters** (causation happening via the media of spaceships, probes, rocks, spores, ejected planets...anything that has a mass), happening at lower speed and limited to lower horizons.

In this section, we will be exploring the particularities of massive [\(a\)](#), then non-massive transmission [\(b\)](#),

a) Impact via massive transmitters

Definition

Impacts via massive transmitters are potential impacts depending on causation happening through the media of massive objects. Due to special relativity, these happen at speeds slower than the speed of light.

Incidental and intentional impacts related to operations involving spaceships, probes, ressources, materials, big or small, classify in this category, and may be direct, or dependent on

³ An allowance exists for errors up 14 orders of magnitude for volume access before the discussion loses its meaning, as per main document, *II,C) on the explored magnitude*

⁴ See *Annex II De Sitter Model*, for detailed explanations on horizons.

the existence of extrasolar life (ET) or intelligence (ETI). As examples of the later, the impact of a directed panspermia is direct. The one of a biological virus is ET dependant, and the one of an idea written on a plate on a probe, is ETI dependant.

limits

For range calculation, two limits are considered: gravitational binding, and horizon due to expansion.

Enroute speed reduction due particles are neglected in this work, but would require more investigation. Exotic possibilities such as speed reduction due to dilatant vacuum⁵, are discarded, being not considered as corresponding to the current paradigm.

It is considered that given the existing time capsules designed to last more than $1.40E+10$ years⁶, the discovery of surviving organisms after 100 million years of slowed down metabolism, and the more general consideration regarding time resistance of lifeforms, presented in the main document⁷, decay along travel time, is not a limiting factor.

Synthesis

Limit 1: Gravitational binding: Depending on its speed, and of its propulsion system, a massive transmitter may or may not be capable of escaping the gravity well of its departing system, or of its galaxy, and so on up to the largest possible gravitationally bound cluster. The limit of such causation is then the first gravitationally bound system containing the Solar System, whose escape velocity is higher than speed of the transmitter. The threshold escape velocities retained for the evaluation are 42km/s, (0.01%c) for the Solar System 0.3%c for the milky way, and 1%c for the Laniakea supercluster. The details on the elements within range are given below in *Table 1. Estimated escape velocities, from the gravitational wells Earth is bound to, with reference to Earth position.*

Limit 2: Horizon due expansion. When the transmitter is travelling faster than all escape velocities, the range is bounded by the speed dependent horizon due to the expansion of the universe: at some point, the universe is expanding faster than the speed of the transmitter itself. Should all escape velocities be exceeded (speed exceeding 1%c), range is considered to be the horizon at the achieved speed, due to the expansion of the universe, calculated using a de Sitter model⁸. The horizon is calculated as v_{∞}/H , where H is the hubble constant⁹, and v_{∞} is the

⁵ [1] (Fedi 2019) *Starshot Failure*

⁶ [2] (Arch Mission Foundation, 2020) *5D Optical Memory Crystal*.

⁷ *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars III*)A)3. *Time resistance*

⁸ See: *Annex II De Sitter Model*

⁹ approximated in 2019 to be $H = 74,03 \pm 1,42$ km/s/Mpc

limit speed of the transmitter after leaving the largest gravitationally bound system it is capable of leaving. v_∞ is referred to as the hyperbolic excess speed, given by $v_\infty = \sqrt{v_0^2 - v_e^2}$, where v_0 is the initial speed of the transmitter, and v_e is escape velocity of the largest gravitationally bounding system being escaped.

Table 1. Estimated escape velocities, from the gravitational wells Earth is bound to, with reference to Earth position.

Embedding clusters, by increasing size	Distance to center (ly)	Solar Masses	Radius or semi major-axis (ly)	Major galaxies	Calculated Ve (km/s)	%c
Solar System	2E-05	1E+00	3.25	0	42	0.01%
Milky Way	3E+04	8E+11	1.90E+06	1	939 (550)*	0.31%
Local Group (Milky Way +Andromeda and satellites)	2E+06	2E+12	1.00E+07	2	186	0.06%
Virgo Cluster**	6E+07	1E+15	7.50E+06	1300	714	0.24%
Virgo SuperCluster**	7E+07	1E+15	5.50E+07	10000	801	0.27%
Laniakea*** supercluster (including great attractor).	3E+08	1E+17	5.20E+08	150000	3,359	1.12%

Escape Velocity:

Escape velocity is the speed at which an unpropelled massive element will be capable of escaping a region under gravitational influence. Using the formulae for a shell mass distribution, values above are approximated with $V_e = \text{SQRT}(2 \cdot G \cdot M / r)$ where r is the distance to the barycenter, M , is the total mass and $G \approx 6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. The considered regions are the ones the Solar System belongs to.

The most massive structure hereby considered to constrain the trajectories of massive transmitters originated from the Solar System is Laniakea supercluster, containing the virgo supercluster, itself containing the virgo cluster, home of the local group consisting of dwarfs galaxies orbiting Andromeda and the Milky Way, where the Solar System is located.

**In the case of the milky way, a better value is retained than our approximation, of 550km/s calculated thanks to the dataset of GAIA mission¹⁰, coherent with more detailed models proposing 455-630km/s¹¹*

¹⁰ [3] (Monari et al. 2018) The escape speed curve of the Galaxy obtained from Gaia DR2...

¹¹ [4] (Sesana et al. 2007) Hypervelocity stars and the environment of Sgr A*

Coherence over time

***only the central part of Virgo clusters and superclusters, within a radius of 17-32e6 ly, are to stay gravitationally bound and maintain coherence in the distant future, the outer elements will disperse with expansion. Being beyond this distance, the local group will recede and eventually become isolated.¹²*

****Laniakea superclusters may not be considered as gravitationally bound, and will disperse in sub clusters such as virgo superclusters.¹³*

b) Impact via non-massive transmitters

Definition

Impacts via non-massive transmitters are happening at the speed of light. What we are addressing here relates to electromagnetic signals, but the analysis keeps validity for all signals travelling at lightspeed, such as for example gravitational waves.

Incidental and intentional information transfer, signaling or messaging via radio or lasers, classify in this category.

Direct potential impact transmitted by signals, such as the impact of the energy of a signal upon arrival, are considered negligible. Potential impacts consecutive to the transmission of information, such as photons carrying the information on the existence or the habitability of Earth, are considered to require the intelligent processing of the information upon reception, and as consequence, are considered as ETI dependant.

As a consequence of disregarding potential direct impacts, all impacts via non-massive transmitter are here below considered as ETI dependant. As such, while the estimated ranges might be strong evaluations, the reliability of the evaluations corresponding to impacted elements via this mean are considered weak, as per the proposed classification of reliability.

limits

The space within which such impacts may happen is the one where information may be sent onboard signals, and where the signal may be detected against background noise. This limit of selectability of the signal against the background noise is calculated, and is dependent on the receiver. As a consequence, for the purpose of proposing an evaluation of the scope of opportunity accessible via non-massive transmitters, it is necessary to provide assumptions regarding the capability of ETI for being impacted, which are a function of their projected

¹² [5] [\(Chon et al. 2015\) On the definition of superclusters](#)

¹³ [5] [\(Chon et al. 2015\) On the definition of superclusters](#)

capability. The scope for impact via a non massive transmitter is considered to be bounded by the maximal range for the detection of the considered signal. Which is ET dependent, and function of the chosen typical alien, which is discussed just below.

5-The hypothesis of extraterrestrial life

As explored in [4-Transmission type](#), some of the impacts via massive transmitters, and all of the considered impacts via non-massive transmitters, require some form of extrasolar life to exist. To try and assess this question of ET which may not be escaped when considering life's advents out there, we will distinguish:

- **Direct impacts**, as directly caused by the Solar System originated life. As an example, the colonisation of a desert planet by life from earth, classifies as a direct impact.
- **ET-dependent impacts** as impacts, through the medium of possible extrasolar life (ET). The eradication of a local biodiversity on a colonised planet is for example ET-dependant
- **ETI-dependent impacts**, are impacts, through the medium of possible extrasolar intelligent life (ETI). The detection by ET of an intentional message from us, such as the reading of the golden plate on Voyager probes, would as such qualify as ETI dependant.

In this section, in [a\) Stars hosting planets in their habitable zone](#) we will start by selecting a working hypothesis regarding the habitability of the extrasolar worlds, by the liquid water criteria. This parameter is important to our evaluation, for it conditions the amount of worlds that could potentially be settled by life as we know it on earth, while being also potentially related to the distribution of ET out there. With a cautionary warning regarding weakness, detailed in [b\) Specific caution regarding the distribution of life and intelligent life](#), we will then, in [c\) Decision regarding the evaluation of ET related parameters](#), take a decision regarding the choice of working parameters regarding the distribution of life and intelligent life in the universe, which will allow us to propose representations easier for us to identify with.

a) Stars hosting planets in their habitable zone

The frequency of planets in the habitable zone of their star is a parameter equally important for the potential direct impact of colonisation of those planets by life originating from the solar system, and for setting an upper bound to the frequency of ET, when it is considered that ET is rather similar to life on Earth and requires liquid water to live.

Amongst the 4215 confirmed exoplanets by sept 2020, 336 are considered to be in the habitable zone of their star, when defined from the liquid water criteria¹⁴. The set includes detection to the galactic bulge, and is proposed to begin to be statistically pertinent. Considering that the gaseous giants in this set may harbour moons, which would then be in the habitable zone too, a non exceptionalist approach leads to a maximal frequency of habitability (liquid, surface water) of 8% per planet, which happen to be coherent with what is happening right now in the Solar System where only Earth lays in habitable zone.(11%). For the purpose of our evaluation of scope, a frequency of 10% per planet will be retained. This estimation is considered as strong, thanks to the size of the set, and thanks to the variety of locations of the considered planets in the galactic environment.

Modern discussion evaluate the average number of planets per stellar system to be 0.2–1¹⁵. In our case we are interested in providing maximal estimates hence 1 will be retained, and the frequency of habitability per stellar system will be considered to admit an upper strong bound of 10%.

b) Specific caution regarding the distribution of life and intelligent life

Life and intelligent life are objects that are alone in their class. We only have Earth as an example. The strategies for inferring probabilities out of such minimal knowledge, take ground on the size of the investigated environment, where no other object of the class has been found. This is the starting point of bayesian approaches, single point statistics and of an entire class of inferences reclaiming from variants of the copernican principle¹⁶. The underlying and shared assumption of those methods is that the frequency of the searched object shall be in relation with the size of the searched environment, where it has not been found. This logic does not only apply in space, and similar approaches are used along time, to try and extract generic information from the investigated history of Earth where life, and technological civilisations only

¹⁴ Nasa exoplanet catalog, accessed 15/09/20 from [exoplanet app](#).

The habitable zone is defined in Annex I Solar System 6-Habitable zone.

¹⁵[6] ([Petigura et al. 2013](#)) [Prevalence of Earth-size planets orbiting Sun-like stars](#)
& [7] ([Cassan et al. 2012](#)) [One or more bound planets per Milky Way star...](#)

¹⁶ As an example see [8] ([Westby and Conselice 2020](#)) [The Astrobiological Copernican Weak and Strong Limits...](#)

appeared once.¹⁷ Sadly, these estimation of frequency from empty search space, does not stand when distributions are discontinuous at the considered scale.:

Fig 1. Drawing: estimations of frequency from empty search space are dubious when distributions are not continuous.

Spacewise, Fig 1. above, graphically demonstrate this ad absurdum. Then timewise, the story of the turkey assessing its history of a lazy comfortable life and concluding that it is going to have another beautiful day on the morning of thanksgiving, is giving us another warning regarding these approaches.

As a conclusion to this cautionary word, our perspective is that the attempts to estimate reasonable possibilities regarding the distribution of life and intelligent life in the universe, is prone to extreme incertitudes, and ultimately, could be anywhere between zero and one. It cannot be exactly zero, otherwise we wouldn't be alive and we are. It can't be exactly 1 either, otherwise we would presumably have spotted it already¹⁸. Very little more may be extracted from the observed absence where we've looked for it, and all the inferences on frequencies

¹⁷ From the simple constatation that the emergence of life was early, and the one of civilisations, late, a recent bayesian approach for examples leads to betting odds > 3:1 that abiogenesis is a rapid and common process, and of 3:2 that intelligence is rare [9] (Kipping 2020) An objective Bayesian analysis of life's early start and our late arrival

¹⁸ unless it is hiding extremely well...

related to the searched space with no encounter, are based on the assumption of some continuity of the would be distribution. Sadly, there is no specific reason for it to be the case, especially when abiogenesis is rare.

c) Decision regarding the evaluation of ET related parameters

In this context of incertitude, it could be tempting to abandon evaluations related to the frequencies of ET or ETI. The decision is made to propose some, for the purpose of triggering imagination. We will do so with multiple warnings regarding the assertiveness of such estimation. Also, we will propose, for the reader to make up his own mind regarding these hypotheses, an online tool where the weakest ones will possibly be tuned and played with.

For selecting the weak estimation presented below, and used later for the evaluation of impacted lifeforms, or extraterrestrial civilisations, the choice was made to optimise for:

- The maximal possible frequencies, in the hypothesis of continuous distributions.
- Coherence with the observed absence of life and communicating life in their respective search space.
- Coherence with the amount of ETI being inferior to the one of ET.
- Coherence with the upper bound set for the habitability, of to 10% per star, considering that postulative ET is dependent on a liquid water habitable zone.

The detailed reasoning is found to be of little importance, and is available upon demand. The resulting generic parameters for ET and ETI are presented below.

Caution, weak estimations ! Generic parameters for ET and ETI

When considering ET or ETI-dependent scopes, the estimation of the probable density of ET or ETI is required. In the present work, we consider frequencies of **1e-7 per star for ETI**, and **2e-3 per star for ET**. These estimation relate to the classic parameters in the Drake equation as defined in¹⁹, in the below way:

f_{li} ~ 1, the fraction of favorable planets on which life does develop

f_i ~ 0.15 the fraction of such inhabited planets on which communicating intelligent life arises

¹⁹ [10] (Tsumura 2020) [estimating survival probability using the terrestrial extinction history...](#)

L ~ 5 Gyr, the mean survival duration of life in the stellar system. Constrained from $F(ETI)$, $F(ET)$ and $f_i \cdot L_i \cdot f(ET) = L \cdot f(ETI)$, for a maximal possible frequency of biosphères;
 $L_i ~ 1700\text{yr}$, the mean lifetime of communicating intelligent life. Constrained from relative frequencies of ET and ETI, for a maximal possible frequency of biosphères.
 $K ~ 4e-13$ Mean rate of habitable planets being born with star formation, averaged over the lifetime of the considered region. When estimated from $R^ \cdot f_p \cdot n_e \sim 0.1^{20}$ and $\sim 250e9$ stars in the milky way.*

Once those parameters are settled, the question stands for any given causation, whether the postulated ET or ETI is sensitive or not to the potential transmission via massive or non-massive vectors. This again is a very postulative task.

With the calculated Drake parameters optimised above so as to evaluate the maximal probability for life, coherent with the absence of observed intelligent life, the mean age of the typical communicating ETI is calculated to be 850 years. This gives some time for developing technologies, but not too much. Given this, and following the observation that the advent of space age as far as we are concerned, as also technologically augmented the odds of self extinction, the decision is taken to use a near term technological advance, for the typical ET detection capability in this work:

Caution, weak assumption: the susceptibility of the typical ET and ETI

ET: Out of alternatives, in the proposed evaluation, ET is considered to behold similar properties to the ones of life as we know it, and hence, share its susceptibility to external impacts. In particular,

- Extraterrestrial life is supposed to be roughly similar to life on Earth.
- ET is considered to be sensitive to ressources disponibility and to invasive species, hence potentially disrupted by any newcomer²¹

ETI, as a class of ET, adds the bellow sensibility:

- Full-Sky survey: ETI is considered to conduct a full sky automatic survey, using a network of 1m telescopes, capable of detecting magnitudes of 20, actively looking for

²⁰ [10] (Tsumura 2020) estimating survival probability using the terrestrial extinction history...

²¹ [11] (Mooney and Cleland 2001) The evolutionary impact of invasive species

other ETIs. As such, it is considered that any signal reaching ETI at a 20 magnitude is to be detected. The range for a magnitude of 20 is hence the one at which there is a 100% probability of being detected.

- Focus: ETI is considered capable of picking up signals at magnitude 30 (equivalent to VLT or Hubble), should it be looking in the proper direction.

6-Points of evaluation

Five evaluation points are proposed, with the below titles:

- Historical opportunities: $\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$
- Opportunities ex mankind: $\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex man}}$
- Opportunities today: Ω_{2020}
- Breakthrough opportunities Ω_{2040}
- Total opportunities Ω_{∞}

$\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$

Evaluation of the historically potentially accessed universe, by life. The estimations are based on the historical approach from *Annex III History*.

$\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex mankind}}$

Evaluation of the potentially accessed universe, by life as we know it with its capability in 2020, excluding the contribution of mankind. The earlier work on the history of access is used for this evaluation.

Ω_{2020}

Evaluation of the potentially accessed universe by life, today including via the media of human spatial activities as per 2020 demonstrated capabilities.

Ω_{2040}

Only 12 years separate Sputnik and the first moonwalk. In the below discussion, we will use the Breakthrough Starshot project, the possible trajectory for light sails allowing nearing 20%c

without the support of a laser, and the Arch Mission Foundation, as a reference for near future opportunities, taking places possibly 20 years ahead. As discussed in the main document, Breakthrough Starshot project is advocated as realistic within 20 years²², the Arch Mission Foundation time capsules are operational today²³, and the navigation of solar sails, envisioned in near term future²⁴

Ω^∞

Imagination, and fantasy, may push way further the hypothetical capabilities of evolving life and technology, hence the size of the universe accessible to it. Science fiction is filled with wormholes, warp drives, spins, teleportation. In our case, evaluating opportunities on the grounds of the scientific understanding of the universe, the speed of light as an absolute speed limit today stands, and so does the horizon involved by the expanding universe. To calculate the total opportunities, we will consider that the ultimate physical limit of the event horizon, proposed by the literature to be 15,7Gly²⁵ away, bounds the possible impact of both massive and non-massive transmitted causation.

Ultimate possibilities regarding frequencies and total transmissions are considered impossible to estimate, while existent, due to limited resources. these are denoted as N/A

7-Evaluation of scope

Having defined the scope, and assumed a neutral moral position regarding the extrasolar advent of life, we've distinguished potential impacts using transmission type and dependency to the hypothesis of ET. The limitations of causation via massive and non-massive transmitters have been detailed, and the dependency to ET been discussed. Typical ET and ETI have been defined, allowing for the evaluation of impacts dependent on their presence. Pertinent points of evaluation have then been defined allowing to investigate the magnitude of the change in potential impact, induced by our potential decision.

In this section dedicated to the evaluation of scope, in [A\) Massive transmitters](#), we methodically evaluate the maximal potential frequency, range and total of impacts via massive

²² [12] [\(Parkin 2018\) The Breakthrough Starshot system model,](#)

&[13] [\(Lubin 2016\) Implications of Directed Energy for SETI,](#)

²³ [14] [\(Arch Mission Foundation, 2020\) 5D Optical Memory Crystal.](#)

²⁴ [15] [\(Heller et al. 2017\) Optimized trajectories to the nearest stars...](#)

&[16] [\(Heller and Hippke 2017\) Deceleration of High-velocity Interstellar Photon Sails...](#)

²⁵ [17] [\(Margalef-Bentabol et al. 2012\) Evolution of the cosmological horizons in a concordance universe](#)

transmitters, at each of the above defined evaluation points, by differentiating intentional access, resulting of the intention of humans, in [A.a](#)), and unintentional one, resulting of potential incidental access, in [A.b](#)), before proposing in [A.c](#)) a recapitulative table regarding impacts via massive transmission.

Then in [B\) Non-massive transmitters](#), at each of the evaluation points, we detail the estimation for the detection range from a remote place (including the reliability of the estimation) :

- with the naked eye (magnitude 6), of an anomaly in the Solar System (strong)
- with an automated survey using 1m telescopes (magnitude 20), of a signal from the Solar System (strong)
- with hubble of VLT type telescopes (magnitude 30), of a signal from the Solar System (strong)
- via the method of transit, of a planet in the habitable zone of the Sun (weak due to small dataset)
- via the method of transit, and the detection of biomarkers in the atmosphere, of life in the Solar System (weak due to small dataset)

Figures supporting the estimations, in [B.b](#)), and a synthesis table in [B.c](#)), are proposed for reference.

The above estimation being made, of the range of massive and non massive potential transmissions, and of the maximal frequency and totals of some of the massive transmission, the evaluation of the impacted elements within accessible volume is undertaken in [C\) Impacted elements](#). To proceed, after important considerations on growing incertitudes are explored in [C.a](#)), the methodology is detailed for the evaluation of the accessible mass and amount of stars within reach, in [C.b](#)), before to proceed with the estimation, using the precedingly evaluated ranges for massive and non massive transmission, of the quantity of significative impacted elements, as listed below for reference (including the reliability of the estimation):

In [C.c](#)), we investigate the quantities within reach, via massive transmitters, of:

- Solar masses (M_{\odot}), and quantity of equivalent solar mass energy ($1.8e+47J$), which is also a proxy for the amount of accessible stars, and Planets²⁶ (strong)
- Quantity of corresponding Milky galaxies (strong)

²⁶ Considering an average of one 0.2-1 planet per star as per [6] ([Petigura et al. 2013](#)) [Prevalence of Earth-size planets orbiting Sun-like stars](#) & [7] ([Cassan et al. 2012](#)) [One or more bound planets per Milky Way star...](#)

- Habitable planets by liquid water habitability (10% of planets) (strong) - Overall potential stellar biospheres - Overall possible amount of solar biomass (weak due uncertainty regarding the validity of the liquid water criteria)
- Inhabited planets ($2e-3$ of planets) - ET stellar biospheres, to destruct, colonise, exchange with (weak due ET dependance)
- Intelligence ($1e-10$ of planets)- ET stellar biospheres, with intelligent life, to destruct, colonise, exchange with, be destructed by (weak due ET dependance)
- Routes between habitable stellar systems per liquid water criteria (strong)
- Routes between galaxies (strong)

Then, in [C.d](#): we investigate the quantities within reach, via non-massive transmitters, of:

- Volume accessible to signaling via electromagnetic waves(ly^3)(Mag 30) (strong)
- Corresponding stars (Mag 30) (strong)
- Habitable Systems (Mag 30) (strong)
- Galaxies (Mag 30) (strong)
- Stellar systems from which to be identifiable with a naked human-type eye. (strong)
- ETI detecting us: stellar system hosting ETIs possibly picking us up through automated full sky scanning with 1m telescopes (Mag 20) (weak due ETI)
- ETI to connect with (qtty) (mag 30), with information, signaling, viruses, data, philosophy, political views. - Stellar systems to ideologically colonize - Stellar systems possibly accessed by an informational virus. (weak due ETI)
- ETI under feedback horizon (weak due ETI)
- Interstellar internet: max connections between habitable stellar systems by liquid water criteria (mag30) (strong)
- Max informational connections between different Galaxies (mag 30) (strong)

Recapitulative tables and synthetic figures are proposed for potentially impacted elements for massive²⁷ and non massive²⁸ transmission. A figure combining all information is presented in the main document²⁹

Along this evaluation process, a robustness indication is provided, and the evaluation mentioned as straight, strong or weak, as per the classification proposed in [3\) robustness of](#)

²⁷ Table 4, p26 & Fig 4. p 27

²⁸ Table 5 p29 & Fig 5. p30

²⁹ *Kingmakers, life's gateway to the stars, fig 11 p67*

[evaluation](#). On figures, weak evaluation will be proposed in dashed lines. In tables, results in **bold fonts** are referring to straight or strong evaluation, roman ones, to weak ones.

A) Massive transmitter

Anything physical, such as probes, nanocrafts, spaceships, rocks, asteroids, ejected planets...

A.a) Intentional

Max Frequency

Intentional with massive transmitters

$\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$: 2/yr (Voyager 1 and two were sent the same year (our probes are still well within the 3.25ly SOI of the Solar System) (strong)

$\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex Man}}$: Null (strong)

Ω_{2020} : 9/yr. In 2020, 9 Solar System missions do take place. Planning extrasolar missions with similar probes would not be extraordinarily more costly or complex, as demonstrated by Pioneer and voyager missions in the seventies. We consider a rate of 9 extrasolar missions/year to be a realistic maximal frequency as per today standard. (strong)

Ω_{2040} : $\sim 2e3/\text{Yr}$, economic limit retained, on breakthrough starshot project. (weak due to many incertitudes)

Ω_{∞} : N/A

Max total

Intentional with massive transmitters

$\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$: 4: Voyager 1, 2 and Pioneer 10 and 11. (strong)

$\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex Man}}$: Null (strong)

Ω_{2020} : $\sim 2e+7$. Hypothesizing the survival of space technology for ~ 1.700 years, the mean lifetime of communicating intelligent life, as proposed for our settings of the Drake equation, and considering that each launch includes the reasonable probability of intentional life related elements or informational self reproducing elements to be onboard, we get max total $\sim 2e+4$ probes. (weak due too much uncertainty on the survival of our civilisation)

Ω_{2040} : $\sim 3e+06$ transmissions happening over ~ 1.700 years, (Ibidem Ω_{2020})

Ω_{∞} : N/A

Max range

Intentional with massive transmitters

ΩHistorical: $\sim 5e4$ ly (Milky Way), the furthest calculated position for Voyager 2 is 4.3ly off Sirius, 8.6ly away, 296.000 years from now³⁰. Apart from the possibility of a gravitational ejection, our historical probes will most probably never leave the milky way due to their speeds, well below the milky way escape speed (550km/s). (strong)

Ω2020 ex Man: Null (strong)

Ω2020: $\sim 5e4$ ly (Milky Way) galactic range, due to demonstrated speeds being below the galactic ejection speed of 550km/s at Solar System position. (strong)

Ω2040: $\sim 5e9$ ly considering an achieved 20%c, with enroute reaccelerations. (strong)

Ω∞: $\sim 13e9$ ly. While the absolute limidue expansion and speed of light is $\sim 15,7$ Gly, a more realistic upper estimate is proposed here with enroute reaccelerating spaceships at 90%c³¹.(strong)

A.b) Incidental

Where the involvement of mankind is considered, the maximal incidental frequencies are the same as the maximal frequencies for intentional transmission, due to the impossibility to absolutely guarantee the absence of malevolent use or insufficient decontamination. (noted: via Mankind, unintentional)

Max Frequency

Incidental with massive transmitters

ΩHistorical: 1/80.000 years, possible incidental transmission due potential exchanges (collisions, ejections) with stellar systems flying through the Solar System. (strong)

Ω2020 ex Man: 1/80.000 years, same reason (strong)

Ω2020: 9/yr. (Via Mankind, unintentional) (strong)

Ω2040: $\sim 2e3$ /Year (Via Mankind, unintentional) (weak, due uncertainty on launch frequency)

Ω∞:N/A

Max total

Incidental with massive transmitters

ΩHistorical: ~ 56.000 along the 4.5Gy of past history (strong)

³⁰ [18] [\(Voyager - The Interstellar Mission 2020\) NASA Website](#)

³¹ [19] [\(Sandberg 2018 \) Space races: settling the universe fast](#)

Ω2020 ex Man: $\sim 9e+05$, via ejections or collision during flybys, along the 7.6Gy of future possible survivability in the Solar System (life migrating along with the habitable zone).(strong)

Ω2020: $\sim 11e+5$ (natural + via Mankind, unintentional, for 1700 years) (weak)

Ω2040: $\sim 3e+6$ (natural + Via Mankind, unintentional, for 1700 years) (weak)

Ω∞:N/A

Max range

Incidental with massive transmitters

ΩHistorical: $\sim 5e4$ ly (Milky Way). It is hypothesized that while the frequency of stellar flythrough is sufficient to have ejected material within the milky way, the probability of intergalactic ejection is low, when considering the earlier calculated maximal 5% probability that a star made it through the kuiper belt.(strong)

Ω2020 ex Man: $\sim 5e4$ ly (Milky Way). intergalactic ejection is disconsidered due hypothesized low probability (see above ΩHistorical) (strong)

Ω2020: $\sim 5e+04$ ly (Milky Way)(Via Mankind, unintentional) (strong)

Ω2040: $\sim 5e9$ ly (Via Mankind, unintentional) (strong)

Ω∞: $\sim 13e9$ ly. (Via Mankind, unintentional) (strong)

A.c) Synthesis on massive transmission

Table 2. Synthesis on maximal total, frequency and range of transmissions via physical, massive elements such as rocks, spaceships and probes.

Bold font indicate strong estimates: wrong by less than one order of magnitude *Roman font* indicate weak ones: possibly wrong by more than one order of magnitude Details provided in [A.a\)](#) and [A.b\)](#)

MASSIVE TRANSMITTER	Ω Historic	Ω2020 ex man	Ω2020	Ω2040	Ω∞
intentional					
Max frequency (transmission/yr):	$\sim 2e+00$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 9e+00$	$\sim 2e+03$	N/A
Max total (past for historic) (else future) (ly)	$\sim 4e+00$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 2e+04$	$\sim 3e+06$	N/A
Max range (ly)	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 5e+09$	$\sim 1e+10$
Incidental					
Max frequency (transmission/yr):	$\sim 1e-05$	$\sim 1e-05$	$\sim 2e+04$	$\sim 2e+03$	N/A
Max total (past for historic) (else future)	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 9e+04$	$\sim 1e+06$	$\sim 3e+06$	N/A
Max range (ly)	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 5e+09$	$\sim 1e+10$

B) Non-massive transmitters

Transmission via electromagnetic waves, photons, beams, lasers...

Future detectability is growing not only due to the maximal intentional range for messaging, but also due to the leaks of a beamed transport system.

The detection ranges for habitability and life from biomarkers are higher than the ones for intelligence due intentional or unintentional activity, for historical times, and present time. This is to change in the decades to come with the development of Breakthrough type laser arrays.

B.a) Evaluation of the potential for non-massive transmissions

Max range for a naked eye detection of intelligence in the Solar System

ΩHistorical: null (strong, see [13])

Ω2020 ex Man: null (strong, see [13])

Ω2020: 0.3 ly (Via Mankind) (strong, see [13])

Ω2040: 6e3ly(Via Mankind) (strong, see [13])

Ω∞15,7Gly(Via Mankind) technology limited by physics: ultimate **range** is considered to be the event horizon (strong, see *Annex II de Sitter Model*)

Max range for automated survey detection of intelligence in the Solar System

ΩHistorical: 325 ly (unintentional). Amongst the 38 identified METI signals, only 9 transmissions are considered to have been targeted precisely enough, and involving enough power, to have a potential impact. The probability of this is considered negligible. From radar tracking systems, the max max range is 325 ly, 241.000 stars (Max hypothesis retained, (Strong: see main document, *D) Signals.*)

Ω2020 ex Man: null (strong: no non-human broadcast)

Ω2020: 325 ly (unintentional). The maximal range for detection is in present times driven by our radar tracking activity, which is detectable to 325 ly. this value is retained. With our intentional signaling capability today, classified as 1.5 in Lubin's scale, we would be detectable from ~200ly, with 1m telescope(mag 20 sensibility)(Strong: see main document, *D) Signals*, and figure 2 below)

Ω2040: ~2Mly, the retained value is the 2Mly from which a full sky survey at mag 20, with 1m telescope, would detect the Breakthrough Starshot laser in operation. The operational

Breakthrough Starshot laser would lead life on earth to be classified as 3.5 in the Lubin scale.

³² (Strong, from figure 2 below)

Ω_{∞} : 15,7Gly technology limited by physics: ultimate range is considered to be the event horizon (strong, see *Annex II de Sitter Model*)

Max range for detection of intelligence by a small field of view (hubble or VLT type), looking precisely at us while we are targeting it.

$\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$: 600 ly (Strong, signaling range of cosmic call 1³³)

$\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex Man}}$: ~ 0 (Strong, human sole signaling intelligence on earth)

Ω_{2020} : $\sim 20\text{Kly}$, (Strong: estimated using Figure 2)

Ω_{2040} : $\sim 0.2\text{Gly}$ (Strong: estimated using Figure 3)

Ω_{∞} : 15,7Gly technology limited by physics: ultimate range is considered to be the event horizon (strong, see *Annex II de Sitter Model*)

Max range for Habitability detection

$\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$: $\sim 25\text{K ly}$ Sweeping 25K ly range, encompassing the entire galaxy, for a total of 100-400 billion stars. (Strong, see *Annex III, History, incidental signals*)

$\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex Man}}$: $\sim 25\text{K ly}$ (Strong, *ibid.*)

Ω_{2020} : $\sim 25\text{K ly}$ (strong, *ibid.*). (Beyond our present signaling range, of $\sim 20\text{Kly}$, estimated using Figure 2.)

Ω_{2040} : $\sim 2\text{Mly}$ (strong, estimated using Figure 3.). When the signal from a breakthrough type laser is detected, the habitability of the origin may be assumed.

Ω_{∞} : 15,7Gly technology limited by physics: ultimate range is considered to be the event horizon (strong, see *Annex II de Sitter Model*)

Max range for detection of life in the Solar System

$\Omega_{\text{Historical}}$: $\sim 5400\text{ly}$ sweeping 5400ly range, encompassing 1 billion stars. (strong, see *Annex III, History, incidental signals*)

$\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex Man}}$: $\sim 5400\text{ly}$ (Strong, *ibid.*)

Ω_{2020} : $\sim 20\text{Kly}$, estimated using figure 2.)

Ω_{2040} : $\sim 2\text{Mly}$ (strong, estimated using figure 3.)

³² [13] ([Lubin 2016 Fig 3.](#)) [Implications of Directed Energy for SETI](#),

³³ [20] ([Billingham and Benford 2011](#)) [Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale 'Messaging'](#),...

- Ω^∞ : 15,7Gly technology limited by physics: ultimate range is considered to be the event horizon (strong, see *Annex II de Sitter Model*)

B.b) Figures for detectability estimations

Fig2. Equivalent photometric magnitude as a function of distance and transmitting civilisation class: detectability range of a class 1.5 civilisation³⁴

³⁴ Modified figure to outline interesting detection thresholds corresponding to the level of development on Earth today. Initial figure: [13] (Lubin 2016 Fig 3.) Implications of Directed Energy for SETI,

Fig3. Equivalent photometric magnitude as a function of distance and transmitting civilisation class: detectability range of a class 3.5 civilisation³⁵

B.c) Synthesis on non-massive transmission

Table 3. Synthesis of maximal range for extrasolar transmissions via electromagnetic waves of all kinds(laser, radio...).

All estimates considered strong: wrong by less than one order of magnitude, details provided in [B.a\)](#)

NON-MASSIVE TRANSMITTER	Ω Historic	Ω 2020 ex man	Ω 2020	Ω 2040	Ω ∞
Max range for a naked eye detection of anomaly in the Solar System (Mag 6) (ly)	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 3e-01$	$\sim 6e+03$	$\sim 2e+10$
Max range for automated survey detection of intelligence in the Solar System (ly)	$\sim 3e+02$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 3e+02$	$\sim 2e+06$	$\sim 2e+10$
Max range for detection of intelligence by small FOV (hubble or VLT type), looking precisely at us while we are targeting it. (ly)	$\sim 6e+02$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 2e+04$	$\sim 2e+08$	$\sim 2e+10$
Max range for habitability detection (ly)	$\sim 3e+04$	$\sim 3e+04$	$\sim 3e+04$	$\sim 2e+06$	$\sim 2e+10$
Max range for detection of life in the Solar System (ly)	$\sim 5e+03$	$\sim 5e+03$	$\sim 2e+04$	$\sim 2e+06$	$\sim 2e+10$

³⁵ Modified figure to outline interesting detection thresholds. Initial figure: [13] ([Lubin 2016 Fig 3.](#)) [Implications of Directed Energy for SETI.](#)

C) Impacted Elements

The above ranges allow us to evaluate interesting quantities, such as the amount of potentially habitable stellar systems, or potential extraterrestrial biospheres, within reach considering the estimations above, for each of the selected evaluation points. Before digging in the detailed evaluation of these, we will consider the question of incertitudes, which are growing along the process.

C.a) incertitudes are growing

The above calculated ranges are distances, and will be used to extract quantities, from evaluated densities within reachable volumes. As such, when strong estimations of distances, and of density, considered not to be wrong by more than one order of magnitude by our classification³⁶, are used to extract estimations regarding quantities within volume, the incertitudes add up, leading to an incertitude on four orders of magnitude³⁷ for the calculated quantities: reality may be as far as ten thousand times bigger or smaller than our strong estimation on quantities. Considering networks, based on our estimates classified as strong, incertitudes grow to 7 orders of magnitude³⁸.

As a synthesis on incertitudes, table 4. Is proposed

Table 4. Evaluation of incertitudes

Evaluation qualified as strong or straight, in bold font in the provided tables :

- **Distances:** one order of magnitude, reality may be ten times bigger or smaller
- **Volumes:** three order of magnitude, : reality may be 1000 times bigger or smaller
- **Quantities:** four orders of magnitude, : reality may be 10.000 times bigger or smaller
- **Networks:** seven orders of magnitude, : reality may be 10.000 times bigger or smaller

Evaluation qualified as weak, in roman font: incertitudes are worse than the above

³⁶ See 2- Robustness of evaluation

³⁷ One due to distribution, the three remaining due the calculation of volume See *Annex II, de Sitter Model*, table 4, p13.

³⁸ One due to distribution, the six remaining due the calculation of network See *Annex II, de Sitter Model*, table 4, p13.

While those resulting uncertainties are intrinsically enormous, it will be seen along the unfolding resulting estimations below, that these do not alter the significance of the proposed results. Not only are these well within the determined range of 14 orders of magnitude, allowing for errors before the discussion loses importance³⁹, but it also has to be noted that most of the evaluations considered as strong, do have a way higher confidence than the retained order of magnitude. A good example of this is the amount of stars estimated from GAIA Archive at short range, which can be considered exhaustive.

C.b) Accessible mass and amount of stars within reach

The below hypotheses are retained, to estimate the mass within range, and the amount of stars. When the range differs between intentional and incidental transmission, the range retained for the below calculations, is the highest of the intentional and incidental ones.

Range < 5000 ly: amount of stars S estimated from request on GAIA DR2 stellar catalog⁴⁰, with $T > 2000K$ (Straight estimates, from exhaustive stellar detections). Mass estimated using $M = S/0.3$, the average mass per star, averaged on the milky way with $250e9$ stars, and $8e11$ solar masses (including dark matter) (Strong)

5000ly < Range < 4e6ly: estimates based on geometric fractions of the galaxy, considered to contain $250e9$ stars, and $8e11$ solar masses (including dark matter) (Strong, with uncertainties linked to the estimation of the fraction)

4e6ly < Range < 1.2e7ly : estimates based on geometric fractions of the local group, considered to contain $1250e9$ stars ($1000e9$, andromeda, $250e9$, Milky Way), and total $2e12$ solar masses (including dark matter) (Strong, with uncertainties linked to the estimation of the fraction)

Range > 1.2e7ly: mass estimates based on $1.7e-10 M_{\odot}/ly^3$ density of ordinary matter in the universe, with solar mass (M_{\odot}) of $2e+30$. Stars amount estimated from local group ratio, of 0.6 star/ M_{\odot} (ordinary+dark matter). Galaxies amount estimated from the amount of stars, as $G = S/250e9$. (the quantity of equivalent milky way size galaxies). (Strong)

³⁹ See main document, p20, II)C) on the explored magnitude

⁴⁰ [21] [\(Gaia DR2 contents - Gaia - Cosmos\) Access to Gaia database](#)

C.c) Potentially impacted elements, via massive transmitters:

Via spaceships probes, ejected materials...

Here below are detailed calculable quantities of interesting potentially impacted elements, via massive transmitters.

- **Accessible mass (M_{\odot}), and qty of equivalent solar mass energy,(1.8e+47J):** calculated as the maximal amount of stars within the sup of incidental and intentional max range. (Strong)
- **Accessible stars and galaxies:** idem. (Strong)
- **Habitable systems:** Given the earlier estimation⁴¹, we retain 1 planet per star, and 10% of planets being habitable. (Strong)
- **Inhabited system:** Given the earlier estimation, we retain 2e-3/star. (Weak)
- **Systems inhabited by intelligent life:** Given the earlier estimation, we retain 1e-10/star (Weak)
- **Quantity of routes between habitable systems:** calculated as the amount of binomes within the set of n Habitable systems: C_n^2 . Using the upper bounding, $C_n^k \leq \frac{n^k}{k!}$, a maximal bound of $C_n^2 \leq \frac{n^2}{2}$ is used for estimating the maximal amount of routes between habitable systems (Strong)
- **Quantity of routes between galaxies:** similarly bounded by $\frac{G^2}{2}$ where G is the amount of galaxies within reach (Strong)

⁴¹ See [5.a\)](#)

Table 4. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via massive transmitters

by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.

Via spaceships, probes, ejected materials...

Bold font indicates strong estimates: wrong by less than four orders of magnitude (less than seven orders, when considering routes). Roman font indicate weaker ones

Details of estimation provided in text above.

Accessible via massive transmitters	Ω Historic	Ω2020 ex man	Ω2020	Ω2040	$\Omega$$^\infty$
Accessible mass (M_\odot), and qty of equivalent solar mass energy ($1.8e+47J$)	$\sim 2e+05$	$\sim 3e+05$	$\sim 8e+11$	$\sim 9e+19$	$\sim 2e+21$
Stars					
- Accessible stars					
- Planets	$\sim 5e+04$	$\sim 9e+04$	$\sim 1e+06$	$\sim 5e+19$	$\sim 9e+20$
Corresponding galaxies (qty)	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 2e+08$	$\sim 4e+09$
Planets in habitable zone (liquid water)					
- Overall stellar biospheres					
- Overall possible amount of solar biomass	$\sim 5e+03$	$\sim 9e+03$	$\sim 1e+05$	$\sim 5e+18$	$\sim 9e+19$
Inhabited planets ($2e-3$ of planets)					
- ET stellar biospheres, to destruct, colonise, exchange with	$\sim 1e+02$	$\sim 2e+02$	$\sim 2e+03$	$\sim 1e+17$	$\sim 2e+18$
Intelligence ($1e-10$ of planets)					
- ET stellar biospheres, with intelligent life, to destruct, colonise, exchange with, be destructed by	$\sim 5e-06$	$\sim 9e-06$	$\sim 1e-04$	$\sim 5e+09$	$\sim 9e+10$
Routes (Habitable stellar systems)	$\sim 1e+07$	$\sim 4e+07$	$\sim 6e+09$	$\sim 1e+37$	$\sim 4e+41$
Routes (galaxies)	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 2e+16$	$\sim 7e+18$

Figure 4. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via massive transmitters, by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.

Via spaceships, probes, ejected materials...

C.d) Potentially impacted elements, via non-massive transmitters:

Via lasers, radio, any kind of electromagnetic wave, or elements travelling at the speed of light...

Here below are detailed calculable quantities of interesting potentially impacted elements, via non-massive transmitters.

Volume accessible to signaling: (ly^3): volume from which a targeting observer looking at us with a magnitude 30 capable instrument, (such as Hubble or Vlt), could spot us, if we signal to him. Calculated on a spherical volume from detection range at magnitude 30. This provides us with the maximal envelope within which we would be capable of communicating. (Strong)

Stars, habitable systems and galaxies: amount of such elements, from which our signals could be detected with a magnitude 30 telescope, such as Hubble or VLT. (Strong)

Stellar systems from which to be identifiable with a naked eye. Calculated with GAIA-DR2 dataset, with the earlier computed range for naked eye detectability (Magnitude 6). This estimation is interesting, because it allows us to envision our detectability by non technological ETIs. It is probable that the philosophical representation of the universe would have been different if classical philosophers had had visibly signaling lights in their nightskies. While invisible now, a Breakthrough Starshot type capability would render us seable from an naked human-style eye, from 70millions stars, amongst which 7 millions habitable stellar systems, 130.000 potentially inhabited planets, and a 0.6% chance of being seen by an ETI. (Strong)

ETI detecting us: Stellar system hosting ETIs possibly picking us up through automated full sky scanning with 1m telescopes (Mag 20) IF we are targeting these. Amount of stars calculated from GAIA DR2, using the range computed earlier for detectability with 1m telescopes (magnitude 20), and the retained probability of ETI of $1e-10$ /star. It is interesting to note that in this approach, there is a negligible probability of anybody detecting us now (0.002%), while all ETI in the galaxy, estimated to be about 30, do detect us when we reach a Starshot type capability ($\Omega 2040$). (Weak)

ETI to connect with: (qTTY) beyond the question of detection, it is interesting to estimate the maximal ETIs we could connect with, assuming it is equipped with a magnitude 30 capable detection system such as hubble or VLT, and a Breakthrough type laser. We could be influencing and transferring information, signaling, viruses, data, philosophy, political views. Such ETI could also be susceptible to ideological colonisation, or the transmission of informational virus. We would also be susceptible to this, reciprocally. To estimate this, we rely on above calculations for the range of detection at mag 30, the method for the estimation of the quantity of stars, and the probability of ETI. Given the difficulty of estimating the amount of stars within $2e4ly$ ($\Omega 2020$), which is higher than GAIA reasonable exhaustivity range, a rule of thumb is proposed for this to be 25% of the $250e9$ stars in the Galaxy. It is interesting to note that while luck would be required to identify their location, AND for them to pick us if they are not conducting a fullsky survey at Magnitude 30, we have to our hypothesis, already the technological capability of connecting with some ETIs in our Galaxy (6). More, 2040 technology could give us a connection capability well beyond our Galaxy, to 300.000 potential ETI. (Weak)

ETI to have feedback from: With the ongoing expansion of the universe, a question was whether this effect would prevent us a lot, from having feedback to our calls. As it appears, the problem arises over distances where elements are not gravitationally bound i.e. over the local group. It is interesting to note that the possibility to send a signal that cannot be returned due to

expansion, is to arise with Breakthrough class capability. At this stage, only about 12% of reachable places will be capable of responding to us. This will open the moral question regarding whether we are also accountable regarding places we'll never ever have any feedback from. (my opinion: yes) (Weak)

Max connections between habitable stellar systems and between galaxies: calculated similarly to the max routes, above (Strong)

Table 6. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via non-massive transmitters by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.

Via electromagnetic signaling: radio waves, visible light, lasers...

Bold font indicates strong estimates: wrong by less than 3 orders of magnitude for volumes, less than 4 orders for quantities, less than 7 orders considering networks.

Roman font indicate weaker estimates

Details of estimation provided in text above.

Accessible by non-massive transmitter	Ω Historic	Ω_{2020} ex man	Ω_{2020}	Ω_{2040}	Ω_{∞}
Volume accessible to signaling via electromagnetic waves(ly^3)(Mag 30)	$\sim 9e+08$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 3e+13$	$\sim 3e+25$	$\sim 2e+31$
Stars (Mag 30)	$\sim 1e+06$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 6e+10$	$\sim 3e+15$	$\sim 2e+21$
Habitable Systems (Mag 30)	$\sim 1e+05$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 6e+09$	$\sim 3e+14$	$\sim 2e+20$
Galaxies (Mag 30)	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 1e+04$	$\sim 7e+09$
Stellar systems from which to be identifiable with a naked human-type eye.	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 1e+00$	$\sim 7e+07$	$\sim 2e+21$
ETI detecting us: stellar system hosting ETIs possibly picking us up through automated full sky scanning with 1m telescopes (Mag 20)	$\sim 2e-05$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 2e-05$	$\sim 3e+01$	$\sim 2e+11$
ETI to connect with (qtty) (mag 30) with information, signaling, viruses, data, philosophy, political views. -Stellar systems to ideologically colonize via a beam -Stellar systems possibly accessed by an informational virus.	$\sim 1e-04$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 6e+00$	$\sim 3e+05$	$\sim 2e+11$
ETI to have feedback from (at least one)	$\sim 1e-04$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 6e+00$	$\sim 4e+04$	$\sim 2e+10$

Interstellar network: max connections between habitable stellar systems (mag30)	$\sim 6e+09$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 2e+19$	$\sim 6e+28$	$\sim 1e+40$
Intergalactic network (mag 30)	$\sim 5e-01$	$\sim 0e+00$	$\sim 5e-01$	$\sim 9e+07$	$\sim 2e+19$

Fig 5. Quantities of elements potentially impacted via non-massive transmitters, by the human decision regarding the extrasolar advents of life as we know it on earth.

Via electromagnetic signaling: radio waves, visible light, lasers...

Bibliography

1. Marco F. Significant deceleration and mission failure, due to dilatant vacuum, expected for the Breakthrough Starshot programme. Available: <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01999020/document>
2. 5D Optical Memory Crystal — Arch Mission Foundation. [cited 13 Oct 2020]. Available: <https://www.archmission.org/5d-optical-memory>
3. Monari G, Famaey B, Carrillo I, Piffl T, Steinmetz M, Wyse RFG, et al. The escape speed curve of the Galaxy obtained from Gaia DR2 implies a heavy Milky Way. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*. 2018. p. L9. doi:10.1051/0004-6361/201833748
4. Sesana A, Haardt F, Madau P. Hypervelocity stars and the environment of Sgr A. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society: Letters*. 2007. pp. L45–L49. doi:10.1111/j.1745-3933.2007.00331.x
5. Chon G, Böhringer H, Zaroubi S. On the definition of superclusters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*. 2015. p. L14. doi:10.1051/0004-6361/201425591
6. Petigura EA, Howard AW, Marcy GW. Prevalence of Earth-size planets orbiting Sun-like stars. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2013;110: 19273–19278.
7. Cassan A, Kubas D, Beaulieu J-P, Dominik M, Horne K, Greenhill J, et al. One or more bound planets per Milky Way star from microlensing observations. *Nature*. 2012;481: 167–169.
8. Westby T, Conselice CJ. The Astrobiological Copernican Weak and Strong Limits for Intelligent Life. *The Astrophysical Journal*. 2020. p. 58. doi:10.3847/1538-4357/ab8225
9. Kipping D. An objective Bayesian analysis of life's early start and our late arrival. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2020;117: 11995–12003.
10. Tsumura K. Estimating survival probability using the terrestrial extinction history for the search for extraterrestrial life. *Sci Rep*. 2020;10: 12795.
11. Mooney HA, Cleland EE. The evolutionary impact of invasive species. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2001;98: 5446–5451.
12. Parkin KLG. The Breakthrough Starshot system model. *Acta Astronautica*. 2018. pp. 370–384. doi:10.1016/j.actaastro.2018.08.035
13. Lubin P. Implications of directed energy for SETI. *Planetary Defense and Space Environment Applications*. 2016. doi:10.1117/12.2238212
14. 5D Optical Memory Crystal — Arch Mission Foundation. [cited 13 Oct 2020]. Available: <https://www.archmission.org/5d-optical-memory>
15. Heller R, Hippke M, Kervella P. Optimized Trajectories to the Nearest Stars Using

- Lightweight High-velocity Photon Sails. *The Astronomical Journal*. 2017. p. 115.
doi:10.3847/1538-3881/aa813f
16. Heller R, Hippke M. Deceleration of High-velocity Interstellar Photon Sails into Bound Orbits at α Centauri. *The Astrophysical Journal*. 2017. p. L32. doi:10.3847/2041-8213/835/2/l32
 17. Margalef-Bentabol B, Margalef-Bentabol J, Ceba J. Evolution of the cosmological horizons in a concordance universe. *Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics*. 2012. pp. 035–035. doi:10.1088/1475-7516/2012/12/035
 18. Voyager - The Interstellar Mission. [cited 26 Oct 2020]. Available: <https://voyager.jpl.nasa.gov/mission/interstellar-mission/>
 19. Sandberg A. Space races: settling the universe fast. Future of Humanity institute. 2018. Available: <https://www.fhi.ox.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/space-races-settling.pdf>
 20. Billingham J, Benford J. Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale “Messaging”, and the Need for International Debate on Potential Risks. 2011. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1102.1938>
 21. Gaia DR2 contents - Gaia - Cosmos. [cited 16 Oct 2020]. Available: <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/dr2>